

Bank-Specific and Macroeconomic Determinants of Non-Performing Loans in Tanzania: A Panel Data Analysis

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to investigate the bank-specific and macroeconomic determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in Tanzanian banks. NPLs are red flag, providing signal of jeopardize for a country's economic performance. The NPLs problem has become an alarming issue for bank's sustainability globally. This study collects data from 10 sampled commercial banks in Tanzania over the period from 2019 to 2024, thus yielding 60 bank-year observations. The study performs random effect and fixed effect regression models to get the robust and significant result. Based on random effects regressions results variable Liquidity, GDP and Inflation Rate were found to be statistically significant at 1% level. Liquidity and NPLs had a positive relationship, which means the larger the liquidity bank has the higher NPLs bank will have. On the other hand, real GDP and NPLs were found to be negatively related. Inflation Rate and NPLs were found to have positive relationship, which implies that the higher the Inflation Rate the larger NPLs will be for the banks as customers are struggling to keep up with the cost of living. The study concludes that commercial banks in Tanzania should operate its activities more efficiently and avoid reckless lending along with mandatory capital requirement in order to reduce NPLs and to ensure profit for their shareholders. The findings of the study would provide insight guidelines regarding bank's credit risk management procedures and systems to country's regulatory body in order to design and adopt required prudential regulations in credit policy.

Keywords: *Non-Performing Loans, Inflation, GDP, Liquidity, Panel Data Model, Tanzania.*

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Introduction

Following the global financial crisis occurred for a few times and the succeeding recession in many developed and developing countries have increased firms' defaults, causing significant losses to the financial institutions. Case of Tanzania is no difference where particularly some banks have gone into bankruptcy and liquidation due to various non-performing loans, here after NPLs. If a bank does not receive a timely partial or full payment of a loan advanced to the customer, it should classify this as a problem loan and the value of the loan on the bank's financial statements should be adjusted to reflect this. By recording them in this way financial sector regulators, stakeholders, bank management and other individuals will have a clearer picture of the true value and strength of the bank (Anita *et al.*, 2022). It follows therefore; problem loans are defined as financials agreements wherein the borrowing party did not pay the interest and/or installments according to a structured schedule which is supposed to be followed. In other words, loans will be defined as NPLs when they do not generate income for the bank and consequently cease to be in accordance with the loan agreement (Antwi & Kong, 2023). NPLs are a "financial pollution" (Aliu and Dey, 2021), as well as an important determinant of financial sector

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instability. The harmful effects of NPLs have prompted many academicians and researchers to study them from different viewpoints.

From theoretical and empirical point of views NPLs have been identified as one of the main causes of financial institutions failure, particularly Banks. A failed financial institution brings many negative effects to the entire economy as it distorts national savings and investment. It follows therefore, managing NPLs and maintaining it at an acceptable level is an important task for the stability of Banks as well as the financial system of a country (Bolognesi *et al.*, 2020). In order to manage the NPLs, it is important to understand the bank-specific and macroeconomic factors which determine the NPLs which is the main problem that would be addressed throughout this research paper. Tanzania has experienced high rate of NPLs due to relatively high interest rates and growth in loans as some of the causes of NPLs show that is being influenced by pressure on the banks to retain high lending rates to minimize losses causing borrowers default thus the need to conduct other studies on other determining variables of NPLs on commercial banks (Khan *et al.*, 2020).

Given the brief discussion above, it becomes necessary to identify the bank-specific and macroeconomics determinants of NPLs which is the major motivation for this study. Using panel data modelling, this study empirically investigates the determinants of NPLs in the Tanzanian banking system. The contribution of this empirical study is of twofold. First, it provides evidence of the determinants of NPLs in Tanzania taking into account both macroeconomic and bank-specific factors while using the most recent data set spanning from 2019 to 2024. Secondly, the study applies panel data models which provide more data points, increase statistical efficiency, control for unobserved heterogeneity, and enable the study of dynamic relationships over time.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section two of the paper consists of theoretical and empirical literature review on NPLs globally and Tanzania in particular. Section three provides data type and sources as well as methodology used to analyze sampled panel data. Section four consists of a presentation, analysis and discussion of major findings of the study. Finally, section five consists of a conclusion and recommendations based on the research findings.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

This section of theoretical review in this paper provides some theories related to the determinants of Non-Performing Loans specifically those that are linked macroeconomic variables and bank specific factors. Some of the theories reviewed in this paper include Information Asymmetry Theory, Agency Theory and Financial Intermediation Theory.

Information Asymmetry Theory

The theory of asymmetric information hypothesizes that it may be difficult to distinguish good from bad borrowers, which may result in adverse selection and moral hazards problems, (Keeton and Morris 1987). For adverse selection problems, in the financial market, the borrower that possesses more information on a specific item to be transacted can negotiate optimal terms for the transaction than the lender. The party that knows less about the same specific item to be transacted is therefore in a position of making either the right or wrong choice concerning the loan transaction.

The moral hazard problem, on the other hand, implies that a borrower has the incentive to default on a loan unless there are consequences for his future applications for credit. This result from the difficulty lenders have in assessing the level of wealth borrowers will have accumulated by the date on which the debt must be repaid, and not now of application. If lenders cannot assess the borrowers' wealth, the latter will be tempted to default on the borrowing. It follows therefore; lenders will increase interest rates thus attracting only risky borrowers, leading eventually to the breakdown of the financial market. Generally, Keeton and Morris (1987) argued that commercial banks that tend to take more risks in advancing loans, including in the form of excess lending eventually absorbed higher losses through increased NPLs.

Agency Theory

Jensen and Meckling are credited with developing agency theory (1976). According to the agency theory, there are two parties in any large company such as a commercial bank, the shareholders who are the principals, and the managers who are the agents who is running the business. The shareholders are the principal or the main party because the company belongs to them. As owners of the company, they receive the profit or bear the loss at the end of the day. Managers are the agents because they are hired by shareholder to run the company on day-to-day activities. In principle, the agents are supposed to make decisions in the best interest of the principal. To ensure that agents are effective will require the principal to monitor the agent. Without monitoring, the managers will diverge from the principal's objectives. They will make decisions which enhance their interest at the expense of shareholders. The tendency for agents to act in their own interest instead of the principal is called the principal-agent problem (Bester, 1994). Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) are the factor that measures the efficiency of the managers. This factor indicates the ability of bank management to generate profits by utilizing the available assets of the bank. A more efficient bank management will have a lower appetite for risky loans hence will have fewer NPLs (Bofondi & Gobbi, 2003).

Empirical Literature Review on Non-Performing Loans

Sunday and colleagues (2020) investigated Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in Uganda's commercial banking industry using quarterly data for the period 2002q1 to 2017q2. ARDL and bounds test techniques were employed while controlling for both bank-specific and macroeconomic factors. The findings of the study indicate that NPLs increase with increase in lending rates, real effective exchange rate and unemployment rate while increase in returns on assets and GDP growth rate lower NPLs. Based on the findings, commercial banks are advised to diversify their asset portfolio by holding other income earning assets such as governments bonds, equity so as to reduce on credit risk exposure.

Mahyoub & Said (2021) examine the factors influencing non-performing loans (NPLs) ratio for Malaysian commercial banks from the period 2010 to 2018. Panel data model which includes 15 commercial banks in Malaysia were employed. The finding of the study reveals that capital adequacy ratio is a significant factor in influencing the sample banks' level of non-performing loans. All other bank-specific factors employed in the analysis were found to be insignificant. In addition, based on the results provided by real GDP and inflation, they concluded that economic situation does not impact the non-performing loans level of the sample commercial banks.

Alnabulsi and colleagues (2022) investigate determinants of non-performing loans in the Middle East and North Africa region by exploring the role of bank-specific and macroeconomic factors, particularly in the period of the global financial crisis, as well as the COVID-19 pandemic, as a health crisis that translates to an economic crisis. The study includes 74 banks belonging to 11 MENA countries over the period 2005–2020 and uses the two-stage system generalized method of moment estimator. The empirical findings indicate that the level of non-performing loans is more sensitive to bank specifics than macroeconomic factors. When it comes to macroeconomic factors, macroeconomic environment and institutional quality significantly affect the level of NPLs. However, no significant effect has been detected regarding the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Owonye & Obonofiermo (2022) examined the determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in the Nigeria banking industry between the periods of 2011-2020. The specific objective of the study was to examine the relationship between the measures of bank specific variables; Bank Size, Capital Adequacy, Profitability, Bank Age, Liquidity and Loan to Total Assets and in Nigeria. The findings revealed that Bank Size, Capital Adequacy and Bank Age have significant effect on NPLs but the effect of Bank Size and Bank Age on NPLs are negative while Profitability have negative insignificant effect on NPLs. The findings suggested that Bank Size in relation to total assets should be put in consideration when granting loans.

Akhter (2023) investigates the determinants of commercial bank's NPLs in Bangladesh. The study collects data from 30 sampled commercial banks over the period from 2011 to 2020. The study performs

Random Effect Regression Model, Fixed Effect Regression Model, and one step GMM system to get the robust and significant result. Findings of the study suggest that that firm-specific factors like lag of NPLs, loan loss provision to total equity ratio, equity-to-total asset ratio, capital adequacy ratio, net loan to total deposit and borrowing ratio, return on equity, and macroeconomic factors such as inflation, and GDP ratio are the crucial determinants of NPLs in Bangladesh. The study concludes that commercial banks should operate its activities more efficiently and avoid reckless lending along with mandatory capital requirement in order to reduce NPLs and to ensure profit for their shareholders.

Salas and colleagues (2024) analyze the factors that explain the evolution of banks' non-performing loan ratios worldwide. Researchers used a sample of 1,631 Entities from 111 countries grouped into the eight central regions in the world, with information corresponding to the period 2007–2021. They applied panel data models and an extensive set of both specific and macroeconomic variables. Findings of the study the show that non-performing loan ratio is determined by a series of specific factors, regardless of where or when they operate. The obtained result is helpful to minimize the cost of building Models for the non-performing loan analysis in the world's most critical regions.

Lyimo (2025) investigated the factors that influence non-performing loans (NPLs) for listed commercial banks in Tanzania. Specifically, the study examined the influence of bank-specific factors; return on asset, capital adequacy, licensed bank age, and bank size on NPLs covering the 2015 – 2022 period. The panel data regression model was employed to calibrate the coefficients of the independent variables of the study. The study findings suggest that capital adequacy is significantly inversely related to NPLs. Bank size was also found to be significantly negatively linked with NPLs. However, the age of licensed banks was positively correlated with NPLs.

Ally and colleagues (2025) use a financial technology index alongside bank-specific and macroeconomic variables, with data from 30 Tanzanian commercial banks spanning from 2010 to 2021. They employ a two-step system, a Generalized Method of Moments to tests the hypotheses and provide robust findings. The results reveal that FinTech significantly reduces non-performing loans across all bank categories, with the strongest effects observed in small banks, followed by medium and large banks. This indicates that advancements in FinTech improve credit risk management and reduce loan default rates. Conversely, a cost-to-income ratio and a high loan-to-deposit ratio increase non-performing loans, particularly in medium-sized banks.

Research Methodology

Data

Data for the current study has been extracted from the annual report of 10 commercial banks in Tanzania based on availability of data in the chosen sample period. Subsequently, the sample 10 banks consist of; CRDB Bank plc (CRDB), DCB Commercial Bank plc (DCB), KCB Group Limited (KCB), NMB Bank plc (MNB), National Bank of Commerce (NBC), ABSA bank Tanzania Limited, EXIM bank Tanzania Limited, Amana Commercial bank, STANBIK bank Tanzania Limited and Akiba Commercial Bank. The sample period for the study was eight (6) years from 2019 to 2024, thus yielding 60 bank-year observations.

Static Panel Data Model

In this paper the static panel data which comprises of a combination of cross-section and time series data is tested under the random effects and fixed effects models. The fixed effect model considers that the Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) heterogeneity effects does not change overtime, and the random effect model considers NPLs heterogeneity effects to vary overtime and that it produces an impact on the regression's residuals of the static model.

The fundamental discussion for estimation techniques of a regression model of static panel data is based on the following form:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 + \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_j X_{jit} + \sum_{p=1}^s \gamma_p Z_{pi} + \delta t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where Y is the dependent variable (NPLs), the X_j are observed explanatory variables (Liquidity, Inflation Rate and real GDP), and the Z_p are unobserved explanatory variables, such as other banks specific characteristics apart from liquidity. The index i refers to the unit of observation, t refers to the time period, j and p are used to differentiate between different observed and unobserved explanatory variables. A trend term t has been introduced to allow for a shift of the intercept over time. ε_{it} is a stochastic term assumed to satisfy the following conditions:

$$E(\varepsilon_i) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$Var(\varepsilon_i) = \sigma^2 \quad (3)$$

$$Cov(\varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j) = 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq j$$

These relationships state that the stochastic terms are assumed to have a normal distribution with zero mean and constant variance (σ^2), and that stochastic terms must be independent over time. In practice most of the panel data applications utilize a one-way error component model for the disturbances with

$$\varepsilon_{it} = \mu_i + V_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where μ_i denote the unobservable individual specific effect and V_{it} denote the remainder disturbance. Note that μ_i is not time variant and take into accounts for any individual specific characteristics that are not included in the regression model. The remainder disturbance (V_{it}), changes with individual specific effects and time and can be thought of as the usual stochastic term in the regression models.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

On assessing bank-specific and macroeconomic determinants of non-performing loans (NPLs) in Tanzania, descriptive statistics was performed in order to establish statistical distributions of the variables of interest in the study. Basic statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis was computed and Jarque Bera tests employed.

The study independent variables include Liquidity, Inflation Rate and real GDP while NPLs is dependent variable. From Table 1, it is evident that there are large variations within the maximum and minimum of each data set and lower variations from the mean and median. GDP has the highest standard deviation as well as highest sum of squared deviation and is therefore the most volatile of all the variables while inflation rate is less volatile variable with lowest standard deviation than other variable.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	NPLs	Liquidity	Inflation Rate	Real GDP
Mean	0.07	0.63	0.10	0.10
Median	0.07	0.08	0.10	0.11
Maximum	0.64	9.43	0.14	0.16
Minimum	-0.80	-0.86	0.05	0.03
Std. Dev.	0.22	1.90	0.02	4.51

Skewness	-1.81	3.67	-0.18	-0.09
Kurtosis	10.68	16.12	2.23	1.64
Jarque-Bera	144.42	452.27	1.44	3.77
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.49	0.15
Sum	3.50	30.27	4.80	479.45
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.20	169.79	0.03	956.98
Observations	48	48	48	48

Similarly, Table 1 shows that NPLs and Liquidity are not normally distributed since their computed probabilities for the Jacque-Bera are less than 0.05. On the measurement of asymmetry of the probability distribution, NPLs, Inflation Rate and real GDP spread are negative skewed while Liquidity is positive skewed. Positive skewness means the tail on the right side of the distribution is longer or fatter. Negative skewness is when the tail of the left side of the distribution is longer or fatter than the tail on the right side. The extent of positive and negative skewness indicates the existence of outliers on the distributions.

Panel Unit Root Tests

In this paper different types of panel unit root tests were computed to check whether series are stationary or not; Fisher-type tests using ADF (Im *et al.*, 2003, Levin *et al.*, 2002) and PP tests (Choi, 2001). Table 2 presents the results of the panel unit root tests for selected commercial banks. From the LLC test it shows that there is no unit root in the series NPLs, Interest Rate and real GDP, while Liquidity was found to have a unit root, hence null hypothesis that there is unit root is being accepted. Liquidity was found to be stationery after first difference. From the IPS unit root test variables Liquidity was found to have a unit root, null hypothesis that there is a unit root is being rejected at level for all remaining variables. The Fisher-ADF χ^2 and the Fisher-PP χ^2 tests show that there is no unit root in the variables NPLs and Inflation Rate null hypothesis is being rejected and alternative one that there is no unit root is accepted based on these two tests.

Table 2. Results of Panel Unit Root Tests (Variables at Level)

	LLC t*	TESTS		Fisher-PP χ^2
		IPS W-Stat	Fisher-ADF χ^2	
NPLs	-170.75	-27.13	351.47	435.19
	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)
Liquidity	-1.09	-0.55	3.75	3.78
	(0.14)	(0.29)	(0.71)	(0.70)
Inflatio	-1.92	-0.78	5.14	4.71
	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)
Real GDP	-2.19	-1.71	7.91	8.24
	(0.01)	(0.04)	(0.25)	(0.22)

Panel Cointegration Tests

Cointegration result based on Kao test for selected commercial banks in which the null hypothesis of no Cointegration is being rejected for the panel data model at 1% level of statistical significance as shown in Table 3. This implies that based on cointegration test proposed by Kao we can conclude that the model used in the study is cointegrated and that there is a long-run relationship between variables of interest.

Table 3. Results of Kao Residual Cointegration Test

Test	Results
ADF test	-3.58 (0.00)
Remarks	Cointegration

Note: in the brackets are P values

Estimating Static Panel Data Models

Estimation results for static panel data models for selected commercial banks are reported in Tables 4. Since observations in the data set can be describe as being a random sample from a given population, both random and fixed effects regressions are being estimated and later on Hausman Test for Correlated Random Effects will be used to choose between the two panel data models.

Based on fixed effects regressions variable Liquidity and Inflation Rate are significant at 1% level, while real GDP found to be not statistically significant at any level of significance. Liquidity and NPLs were found to have a positive relationship, which means the larger the liquidity of the banks the higher NPLs will be. Inflation Rate and NPLs are positively related with the regression coefficient of 0.3135.

Based on random effects regressions results variable Liquidity, real GDP and Inflation Rate were found to be statistically significant at 1% level. Liquidity and NPLs had a positive relationship, which means the larger the liquidity bank has the higher NPLs bank will have, this results is in contrast with real GDP and NPLs which are negatively related. Inflation Rate and NPLs were found to have positive relationship with the regression coefficient of 0.3003 which implies that the higher the Inflation Rate the larger NPLs will be for the banks as customers are struggling to keep up with the cost of living.

Table 4. Static Panel Data Model Estimation Results

Dependent variable: NPLs		
Independent Variables	Fixed effects	Random effects
Liquidity	0.088 (0.000)*	0.058 (0.000)*
Inflation	0.314 (0.000)*	0.301 (0.000)*
Real GDP	-0.062 (0.342)	-0.027 (0.000)
R ²	0.223	0.215
Adjusted R ²	0.201	0.192
F-statistic (3, 156)	24.13	191.64
Prob(F-statistic)	(0.000)	(0.000)

Note: Given are P values in parentheses for coefficients, for random effects Wald χ^2 is given for overall significance of the model. * Significant at 1% level, ** Significant at 5% level and *** Significant at 10% level.

In order to examine bank-specific and macroeconomics determinants of NPLs, the study tested the null hypothesis that; Inflation Rate fees does not statistical significant determine NPLs. From Table 4 findings of the study indicates that Inflation Rate is positive statistical significantly determine NPLs at 1% level of significance. This implies that if Inflation Rate increases by 1 unit, NPLs will increase by 0.30 times. Findings of this study are contrary with the results obtained by (Owonye & Obonofiermo, 2022) and (Akhter, 2023) who confirmed a negative relationship between Inflation Rate and NPLs.

In order to examine to what extent real GDP determine NPLs of the selected commercial banks, null hypothesis that GDP does not statistical significant determine NPLs was tested. From Table 4 findings of the study suggest that real GDP negatively influence NPLs of commercial banks in Tanzania and coefficient is statistical significantly at 1% level and hence null hypothesis is rejected. This implies real GDP increases by 1 unit; NPLs of the selected commercial banks will fall by 0.027 times. The findings of this study are in line with the study of Anita and colleagues, (2022), Sunday and others (2020) and Akhter (2023).

In order to assess to what extent Liquidity of commercial banks determine banks NPLs, the null hypothesis that bank liquidity does not statistical significant determine banks NPLs was tested. From Table 4 findings of the study indicate that, bank liquidity positively statistical significantly determines

banks NPLs, hence the null hypothesis is being rejected. This implies that if bank liquidity increases by 1 unit, banks NPLs will increase by 0.058 times. Findings of the study are in line with study of Sunday and colleagues (2020), Owonye & Obonifermo (2022) confirmed bank liquidity had statistically significant effect on the mutual fund performance. Contrary to the findings of this study, Anita and colleagues (2022) and Antwi & Kong (2023) confirmed a negative relationship between bank liquidity and bank NPLs.

Hausman Test for Correlated Random Effects

From practical point of view there is clear distinction between random and fixed effects models. The fundamental question is which model should be used for statistical inference and policy recommendations. The Hausman specification test is used in this study to test for orthogonality of the banks NPLs and random effects. The test is being conducted under the hypothesis of no correlation, both ordinary least square (OLS) in the least square dummy variable (LSDV) model and generalized least square (GLS) are consistent, but ordinary least square is inefficient. Considering the alternative hypothesis, OLS is consistent, but GLS is not. It follows therefore, under the null hypothesis, the two presented estimates should not differ systematically, and a test can simply rely on the difference.

The Hausman specification test is for the fixed effects model against random effects model and results are being reported in Table 5. The test statistic in this study is 55.62 and the coefficient is not statistically significant at any level. Therefore the null hypothesis of no correlation between the individual effects and other independent variables for both models is not being rejected. Implication of the test results is that use for random effects is being preferred rather than fixed effects. Hence it can be concluded that the random effects model is the better choice in this study and is used in making policy implication and recommendations. The results of fixed effects regression is also being provided just for comparison purposes.

Table 5. Results of Hausman Specification Test

	Model
$\chi^2 (K-1)(2)$	55.62
Prob $>\chi^2$	0.35

Note: K = number of explanatory variables in the model

Conclusion

Financial institutions particularly commercial banks are the pivot participant in a country's economy, as its productive investment ensures the country's economic sustainability. For that reason, the stability of banking sector is imperative for economic growth and development, as well as resilience against financial crisis. Bank's stability and sustenance are threatened by its increasing credit risk which results from increasing NPLs. Thus, monitoring NPLs is essential for both individual bank's effectiveness and the economy's financial deepening and widening. The present study has conducted on the bank-specific and macroeconomics factors that influence the NPLs of commercial banks in Tanzania. Based on random effects regressions results variables Liquidity, real GDP and Inflation Rate were found to be statistically significant at 1% level. Liquidity and NPLs had a positive relationship, which means the larger the liquidity bank has the higher NPLs bank will have, this results is in contrast with real GDP and NPLs which found to be negatively related. Inflation Rate and NPLs were found to have positive relationship which implies that the higher the Inflation Rate the larger NPLs will be for the banks as customers are struggling to keep up with the cost of living.

The policy implication of the study is that macroeconomic stability is an important prerequisite for bank stability in terms of reduced NPLs, hence the need for appropriate macroeconomic policies that foster high and stable growth. On the other hand, macroeconomic stability may also be enhanced by introducing prudential banking policies such as setting high bank capital adequacy ratios, which reduce the adverse impact of macroeconomic problems on banks and thereby reduce the likelihood of the banks worsen the

instability. Regarding the growth rate of real GDP, it is strongly recommended that bank management and loan officers should put in consideration the cyclical nature of the economy and avoid advancing risky loans through compromising on the quality of loans during the boom as when the business cycle reverses from boom to bust, the loan quality will deteriorates faster. The Central Bank of Tanzania should also strength its monitoring framework which comprises of macroeconomic prudential indicators such as inflation and real GDP in assessing the stability and soundness of the banking system as both were found to be statistically significant in determining NPLs.

The study analyzed the factors affecting non-performing loans in commercial banks in Tanzania. In order to have a general clear picture of causes of non-performing loans, other researchers can use dynamic panel data and also expand the scope of the study by considering also micro-finances which operate lending activities as financial sector is quite large and comprise other entities rather than banks. Since the study involved only 10 commercial banks, there is a room to consider all commercial banks in Tanzania. This will increase the sample size to capture variations across the banks, create chances of for having more precise, representative and conclusive results for specific sector area. The study categorized factors affecting non-performing loans into bank-specific and macroeconomic factors. Other researchers may wish to include other bank specific factors to examine the causes of non-performing loans such profitability, capital adequacy, bank size and many others.

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